

LINGUOCULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FRENCH WORD "FAMILLE" IN PHRASEOLOGY

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Abstract. In this article, expressions with the lexemes famille in French are interpreted as a special model reflecting the concept of "Family". In particular, different forms of conceptual thinking "Family" are revealed by comparing the lexical meanings of the lexeme famille with the shades of phraseological meaning. That is, this concept has been analyzed with the help of famille component on the basis of "Father" - "Mother" - "Child" - "whole family" - "family outside the family" micro-conceptual concepts.

Key words: concept of family, concept, phrase, shades of phraseological meaning, microconceptual concepts, component.

In French phraseology, expressions with the famille component have their own meaning and characteristics, and they can be broadly analyzed through various linguistic research methods, in particular, conceptually. The main purpose of paying attention to the explanations of this word in dictionaries is to compare the dictionary and phraseological meanings of the word famille. For this, it is appropriate to analyze expressions with the famille component based on the concept of family as a social phenomenon.

The French expressions with the famille component, formed on the basis of the concept of family, serve to define the national characteristics of the French culture and to express the main aspects of the study of the national-cultural identity of the family members, which are suitable for the owners of the French culture. It is known that the semantic shades of existing lexical units in the language are inextricably linked through linguistic and mental activity. M. Chomsky also traditionally defines language as a mirror of human consciousness (1,4).

For example: en famille; famille inadaptée; family situation; a family of gardeners; famille proche; soutien de famille; conseil de famille; big family; famille de robe; Phraseological expressions such as attendre famille are composed of the famille component, so each of them can express the concept of "family", values and national aspects. However, in the French language there are some phrases, that is, some phraseological units with the word famille, which, despite the fact that they have received the famille component in their structure, may express meanings that are somewhat distant from the concept of "family".

French phraseological units within the concept of "family" can be formed not only with the presence of the word famille meaning family, but also with the presence of the names of family members, that is, with the words père, mère, fils and fille. Not all French expressions involving the names of family members may express the meanings within the concept of family. For example, such a situation often occurs in phraseological expressions involving the French word papa, père, i.e. father. In particular, the following phrases include:

à la papa - unhurriedly, leisurely, unhurriedly, calmly;

de papa - outdated, out of date, left over from Almishoh;

le coup du père François - a slap in the face;
le Père Noël - Santa Claus.

During the analysis of phraseological units within the concept of "family", these phrases are distinguished by their unique features in their structural structure. In particular, most of them have the Nom + de + famille structure. For example, consider the following phrases:

- nom de famille - surname;
- fiche de famille - a document containing family information;
- soutien de famille - family support;
- biens de famille - family property;
- chef de famille - head of the family;
- esprit de famille - family friendliness;
- situation de famille - family situation;
- fils (fille) de famille - family man;
- conseil de famille - family advice;
- les médecins de famille - family doctors;
- papiers de famille - family documents;

The form de famille (de la famille) in these examples shows the presence of occasional features in them, and this situation allows to study them as stable phraseological expressions. This form, i.e. the de famille form, can be found not only in noun phrases, but also in verb phrases, as in the above examples. For example: être chargé de famille - to be a family caregiver; être de bonne famille - to belong to an attentive family; être de famille de robe - to be from a wealthy family; expressions such as.

Depending on the type of prepositions used, in addition to the preposition de, the preposition en can also be found in some cases. For example, en famille; laver son linge sale en famille. In phraseological expressions with the concept of "family" in the French language, the form opposite to the occasional form de famille is usually used in the structure of free phrases, mainly in the form de la famille. For example:

- code de la famille - family code;
- planification de la famille - family planning (this combination is more widely used in English: family planning);
- dessin de la famille - a photo with a family image, etc.

Below, we will try to study the semantics of expressions within the concept of family and the structure of their specific semantic field. First of all, if we pay attention to other dictionary interpretations of this lexeme, in the dictionary "Dictionnaire de l'Académie française" (2) the French word famille is Ensemble de personnes unies par le sang ou l'alliance, that is, one a group of people of the same blood is described in the style, and in another source it is described in the style of Ensemble forme par les parents, les enfants et les serviteurs d'une maisonnée, that is, a family team consisting of parents, children and servants (3). If we pay attention to the dictionary meaning of the word family from the perspective of the Uzbek language, it is a group of people living together, consisting of children, clan, generation and spouse, their children and their closest relatives. interpreted as (4.97.) So, the concept of family acquires its own meaning according to the national-cultural characteristics of peoples, in particular, if it is understood that in the French people families are very compact and in some families even servants are taken into account, and in the Uzbek language, due to

the fact that this nation is very family-oriented, it includes a much wider content. It is known that a concept, regardless of its form, is a product of multi-level thinking activity (5, 268).

In fact, based on the lexical content of the lexeme famille, it can be said that the trinity of father, mother and child in its structural structure is the fundamental basis of the semantic content of the phrase. Therefore, when studying the set of expressions with the famille component existing in the French language, it becomes clear that they can be grouped under microconceptual concepts such as "father" - "mother" - "child" - "whole family" - "family outside the family". In this place, the micro concept of "family outside the family" does not mean the concept of "second family" apart from the main family, but "family of relatives" or "a certain category of thing, object, event and group of people". Below is a list of expressions that represent each semantic meaning. If according to the definition of I. A. Sternin, this content specific to the concept of family can be divided into basic and secondary layers, if "father" - "mother" - "child" - "whole family" make up the basic layers, "family outside the family" forms a secondary layer (6, 59). Even if we pay attention to the referential characteristics of these basic lexemes, they can reflect the spirit of nationalism characteristic of the French people (7, 39).

The expressions given above are described in relation to the place of the family in society, covering the family concept. For example, the specific characteristics of the material, spiritual, psychological, age and other components of the family are reflected in the expressions. Among such aspects, the traditional traditions of the family, the harmony and harmony of the family, whether it is a wealthy or middle-class family according to its social origin, family turmoil caused by family disagreements or mutual misunderstandings, are now much more common in western countries. The concepts of homosexuality ("gayness"), a disgusting disease that is becoming popular and attracts many young people, also make up the content of expressions made with the participation of the French lexeme famille.

The conducted analysis shows that the father's microconcept is more productive than the mother's microconcept, and the child's microconcept is more productive than the parent's microconcept. In addition to the family, the family / group scheme consists of several indicators in expressions with the lexeme famille.

These semantic meanings defined within the concept of family, in the lexical meaning of the word famille, mainly include descriptions referring to the family and its constituent members, and in its phraseological meaning, family members, i.e. The duties and responsibilities of father and mother before the family in the social society, family forms and national values in the family are reflected.

As discussed above, among the existing phraseological expressions in the French language, there are many phraseological units that reflect the concept of "family". Among them, expressions with the lexeme famille are important as a unique "model". As above, they can be comprehensively analyzed from different points of view, and as a result of extensive research of such phraseological units as a specific linguistic research object, on the one hand, a solution to some linguistic conceptual problems is found, and on the other hand, the linguistic, cultural, structural - semantic and grammatical, as well as pragmatic and cognitive features can have their own full descriptions. Also, we hope that the study of phraseological units that reflect the concept of "family" in the French language will to a certain extent help to explain their exact position on the lexical-semantic level.

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